

band of $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{N}^+$ ion at 935 cm^{-1} . The $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ at 1580 cm^{-1} and $\delta_{\text{C-H}}$ at 760 cm^{-1} indicate the bidentate nature of 4,5-diazaphenanthrene coordinating through both the nitrogen atoms¹⁸⁻¹⁶. The absence of band at $3200\text{--}3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes attributable to coordinated water molecules indicate that water is not coordinated to the metal ion even in the pentacoordinated species¹⁶.

In the electronic spectra of the octahedral complexes, bands were obtained at ~ 660 , ~ 550 and $\sim 412\text{ nm}$, which may be assigned to ${}^3\text{T}_2 \rightarrow {}^3\text{E}_1$, ${}^3\text{T}_2 \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_1$ and ${}^3\text{T}_2 \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_1$ transitions. The values are consistent with the earlier observations¹⁷.

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Studies on Water Decomposition Product of Iron(III) Peroxychromate by Ion-exchange Resins

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Several peroxychromates have earlier been reported¹⁻⁵ but not iron peroxychromate. Hence, to ascertain the composition of iron(III) peroxychromate the study of its water decomposition product has been undertaken.

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Experimental

Ice-cold solid Fe^{+++} chromate⁴ (1 g) and anhydrous H_2O_2 (2.5%, 20 ml) extracted in ethyl acetate, were mixed together, shaken occasionally and cooled in a freezing mixture for 30 min. Bluish violet iron(III) peroxychromate, soluble in ethyl acetate, was separated as in other cases¹⁻⁵. The oxidising power of the peroxychromate was determined by Na_2AsO_3 and KMnO_4 methods^{1,8} (Table 1).

Many sets of water decomposition product were prepared by decomposing the peroxychromate (20 ml) in contact with water (50 ml). The colourless organic layer was removed and the yellow aqueous layer was exchanged⁶⁻⁸ with Dowex-50 (Na) and Amberlite-120 (Na) resins.

The presence of Fe^{+++} in elutriant and of $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ in effluent was established by usual qualitative tests, R_f values⁹ (elutriant, 0.720; effluent, 0.319; FeCl_3 , 0.725; $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$, 0.312), absorption (aqueous) and ir (KBr) spectra (effluent and $\text{Na}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$: λ_{max} at 233, 315 and 350 nm; sharp absorptions at 950, 890 and 770 cm^{-1}). The concentration of Fe^{+++} and Cr^{VI} in elutriant and effluent was estimated by colorimetric¹⁰ and gravimetric¹¹ methods (Table 1).

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA

Average amount (g) of			Ratio		
Fe^{+++}	Cr^{VI}	Peroxy O_7^{2-}	a :	b :	c
0.00112	0.00315	0.00156	1 :	2.81 :	1.39
Calcd. :					
$+ \text{H}_2\text{O}$					
$\text{Fe}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10})_3 \longrightarrow \text{Fe}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7)_3 + 9\text{O}$			1 : 2.79 : 1.28		
μ_{eff} at 304 K of elutriant-oxinate = 5.936 B.M.					

The changes in pH (4.75-4.85) of a set of water decomposition product, on dilution with measured volumes (25-300 ml) of water, were found almost similar to dichromate solutions⁶⁻⁷.

Results and Discussion

The above findings confirm that the water decomposition product of iron(III) peroxychromate is composed of Fe^{+++} and $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ in the ratio of 1 : 3. Further, the average amounts of the constituents (Table 1) indicate that a very low percentage of iron(III) chromate is converted to peroxy compound. However, the experimental results and inferences are in agreement with the formulation^{1-5,6-7} of iron(III) peroxychromate as $\text{Fe}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10})_3$.

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Disproportionation of 4-Hydroxyazobenzene and Interaction with Copper(I)

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THE reduction of 4-hydroxyazobenzene at low concentration (for obvious reasons of maintaining the monomeric form¹ of the dye in solution) in Clark and Lubs (KH₂PO₄ and NaOH) buffer of pH 5.8-8.0 containing 1 M KCl at the dme gave a single well defined diffusion-controlled wave. The acidic ionisation constant of the compound was 6.7 × 10⁻⁸ under the experimental conditions and varies very slightly (pK_a 7.17 to 7.16) over the concentration range of 0.1-1.0 mM. The E_{1/2} values shifted linearly with the change in pH according to the following equation,

$$E_{1/2} = 0.08 - 0.07 \text{ pH}$$

The determined value of potential, E⁰ was -0.332 V at pH 6.5 which differed from the calculated value by -0.043 V, providing information that the reduction was not reversible. The substituent constants (ρ=0.14 and Σσ=-0.37) were in confirmation with the work of various authors^{2,3}. Several mechanistic pathways have been highlighted earlier^{4,5} for the reduction of azo compounds. The proposed scheme (Scheme 1) of simultaneous protonation and electron transfer process, followed by slow electron attack to form radical (IV) and anion (III) is attributed to disproportionation reaction, presumably due to the strong electron attracting tendency of -OH in the moiety. Depending on the medium, the different set of products would be obtained,

e.g. in acid, aniline (V) and 4-hydroxyaniline (VI), while in base, the latter is the only product. The possibility of remote reaction cannot be ruled out resulting in 4,4'-dihydroxyhydrazobenzene (VII) and aniline (V) in acid and base media respectively.

Scheme 1. Reduction scheme of 4-hydroxyazobenzene.

The addition of Cu²⁺ (stock solution 0.75 mM) in dye solution (0.1 mM) was made in five steps ranging from 0.125 to 0.25 mM resulted in the following changes in the polarograms: (i) The wave height increased, (ii) E_{1/2} shifted towards more negative potential and (iii) wave shape altered. The procedure was reversed with metal ion in cell while the adequate quantities of 4-hydroxyazobenzene was added. The polarograms showed dissimilar characteristics in the sense that a single composite anodic-cathodic wave⁶ crossing base line at -0.24 V was noticed. This corresponds to the E_{1/2} of the cathodic wave of Cu²⁺ in this medium. The height of cathodic and anodic waves being equal favour disproportionation reaction at the dme. The log plot revealed linearity with a slope + 56 mV which indicates irreversible wave nature of Cu²⁺ in this medium. The calculated E_{a/4} - E_{1/4} resulted in αn=0.923, confirming irreversibility. The above observations indicate complexation.

Disproportionation⁷ of Cu²⁺ to Cu⁰ and Cu⁺ possessing high free energy change is a thermodynamically favourable reaction. This would certainly be induced by ligand which itself is capable of disproportionation. Stability parameters of complexes of Cu²⁺ with the ligand in terms of changes in diffusion coefficient were evaluated by the method developed by Crow⁸, which incorporates the change in diffusion current due to complexation in terms of ligand number, i.e.

$$\Delta i_d \propto n.$$